

Pinellic acid generation in whole wheat products: Impact of linoleic acid content and lipoxygenase activity

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Abstract

The impact of linoleic acid concentration (precursor) and lipoxygenase activity in whole wheat flour on the biosynthesis of the bitter compound pinellic acid in dough were investigated. Utilizing wheat knock out (KO) lines for lipase (LIP), lipoxygenase (LOX) and a double lip/lox KO, the LOX variant was reported to significantly reduce pinellic acid formation in comparison to their wild-type controls. Further mapping of two hundred and twenty US hard wheat varieties indicated there was no correlation between the linoleic acid concentration (or lipoxygenase activity) and pinellic acid generation in the dough. However, differences in lipoxygenase activity were evident between Hard Red Winter (HRW) and Hard White Winter (HWW) wheat classes. These findings indicated that lipoxygenase is a key enzymatic step in the generation of pinellic acid in commercial wheat samples however biosynthesis is impacted by other enzymatic steps or factors.

Keywords: pinellic acid, linoleic acid, lipoxygenase activity, bitterness, whole wheat bread

Introduction

Whole grains are rich in vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, and health-promoting fibres. Health benefits associated with whole-grain intake have been linked to a reduction of chronic pathological conditions including heart disease, cancer, diabetes, and a reduced risk of weight gain [1]. The U.S. Department of Agriculture USDA recommends that at least half of all grain intake should be from whole grain sources [2]. Based on the data obtained from the 2001-2004 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANS), nearly everyone (96.2% to 99.9%) in each sex-age group failed to meet the recommendations for whole-grain [3]. Aversive flavour attributes, such as bitterness, challenge the development of high quality products, limiting whole-grain consumption [4]. Bitterness from added germ extract during bread making has been shown to decrease consumer liking of whole wheat bread. In addition, previous studies have reported that some oxylipins, like pinellic acid, are the most influential bitter compounds in whole wheat bread crumb [5] and also one of the most predictive compounds of dislike in whole wheat bread [6]. Moreover, pinellic acid is generated more than 30-fold upon flour hydration and is thought to be produced primarily through the lipid oxidation pathway (LOX) [7].

Oxylipins, in plants, have an important signalling function that regulates developmental processes, such as pollen formation or mediation of environmental responses that include healing and defensive reactions (antimicrobial). They are usually biosynthesized by the oxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) by different enzymes at different positions of the fatty acid backbone. Trihydroxy oxylipins, including pinellic acid, were initially characterized by Graveland [8] through the study of enzymatic (lipoxygenase) conversion of linoleic acid in dough and flour-water suspensions to oxidized fatty acid isomers. This pathway in plants plays an important role in response to stress and innate immunity [9]. Further, pinellic acid is recognized as a bioactive molecule with antifungal [10] and potent adjuvant activities [11], as well as a bitter taste in aqueous bran and whole meal suspensions [12, 13]. Thus, the understanding of the chemistry which influences the production of pinellic acid, and the mechanism of formation is valuable to develop a strategy to control bitter off-flavour.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents

Ethanol (absolute, HPLC grade), MeOH (HPLC grade), isopropanol (Optima, LC/MS grade), formic acid (Optima, LC/MS), acetic acid (Optima, LC/MS), acetonitrile (Optima, LC/MS grade) were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Fair Lawn, NJ, USA). Water was purified through a Barnstead Nanopure Diamond water purification system (Thermo Scientific, Dubuque, IA). Quick Start™ Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) Standard Set and Quick Start™ were purchased from Bio-Rad (Berkeley, CA, USA). 3-(di-methylamino) benzoic acid (DMAB), 3-Methyl-2-benzothiazolinone (MBTH), the haemoglobin from bovine blood, Tween 20, Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) solution, linoleic acid, and ¹³C-linoleic acid were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Internal reference compound Leucine-enkephalin was purchased from Waters (Waters Co.). Schaftoside standard

was purchased from BOC Sciences (Shirley, NY, USA). Prostaglandin F₂ α (purity \geq 98%) was purchased from Cayman Chemical (Ann Arbor, MI, USA).

Whole wheat flour samples

Two hundred and twenty whole wheat varieties developed in the USA from 1873 to 2016 were provided by the Poland Lab and Wheat Genetics Resource Center at Kansas State University (WGRC), one of the world's most comprehensive collections of wheat germplasm. All seeds analysed were sourced from wheat grown in 2016, from the same growing region. Seed samples were ground to fine homogenous flour in 4 mL reinforced PE vials containing one 3/8" stainless steel grinding ball using GenoGrinder (1300 rpm, 150 seconds) for further analysis. Additionally, HRS lipoxygenase knockout (Lpx KO), lipase knockout (Lip KO), and double knockout of lipoxygenase and lipase (Lip*Lpx KO), as well as their corresponding wild-type HRS control wheat lines were sourced from Arcadia Biosciences (Davis, CA) and milled by Ardent Mills.

Quantification of Pinellinic Acid and Linoleic Acid by Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry (UPLC/MS/MS)

For the analysis of pinellinic acid in dough samples, 15 mg of flour was first transferred to a 2 mL Eppendorf tube followed by the addition of one 1/4 inch stainless steel mixing ball, then 12 μ L (4:5 water/flour ratio) was added to the flour and dough formation was carried out through mixing using GenoGrinder at 1000 rpm for 5 min. Then, an extraction mixture of 1 mL of solvent (1:1 IPA/H₂O, v/v) spiked with internal standard (prostaglandin-F₂ α (PGE-f₂ α), 1 μ g/mL) was added to the dough for solvent extraction. Samples were sonicated for 10 min followed by shaking using the GenoGrinder at 1000 rpm for 10 min. Samples were then diluted 1:50 and sample clean-up was carried out using a 96-well Oasis PRiME HLB plate (1 cc, 30 mg sorbent). After sample loading (250 μ L) and washing (750 μ L, 10% acetonitrile (aq.) with 0.1% formic acid) steps, the retentate was eluted with 500 μ L 90% acetonitrile (aq.) with 0.1% formic acid. Samples were further diluted to 2 mL using water with 0.1% formic acid. The quantification was made by the standard addition method using a 6-point calibration curve. Concentrations ranged from 0.24 - 500 μ g/mL.

For the analysis of linoleic acid in flour, 50 mg was transferred into 2 mL Eppendorf tubes (triplicate for each variety), followed by the addition of one 1/4 inch stainless steel ball. An extraction solvent mixture (2:1 MeOH:DCM, v/v) was added followed by the addition of 50 μ L of ¹³C₁₈-linoleic acid as an internal standard (10 μ g/mL final concentration). The mixture was homogenized using a GenoGrinder at 1000 rpm for 10 min. Samples were then centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 5 min. An aliquot (100 μ L) of the supernatant was diluted 1:10 with MeOH, and sample clean-up was carried out using a 96-well Oasis PRiME HLB plate (1 cc, 30 mg sorbent) utilizing a pass-through method (200 μ L load followed by elution with 500 μ L of MeOH). Samples were further diluted with 300 μ L of water. An external standard calibration curve was prepared using 7-points ranged g from 31 - 2000 ng/mL.

LC/MS/MS analysis was conducted using a Waters ACQUITY H-class UPLC system coupled with a Xevo TQ-S mass spectrometer (Waters Co.). Quantitative analysis was conducted using MRM acquisition mode. MS conditions employed included a capillary voltage of 2.2 kV, sample cone voltage of 50V, ESI⁻, a source temperature of 150°C, and a desolvation temperature of 550 °C. Chromatographic separation was performed on an ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 1.7 μ m column (2.1 mm \times 50 mm) (Waters Co.) kept at 40 °C. Nanopure water with 0.1% formic acid (solvent A) and 9:1 acetonitrile/isopropanol with 0.1% formic acid (solvent B) were used as mobile phase. Flow rate was set to 0.5 mL/min and a solvent gradient program of 25% B (0.0 - 1.0 min), 25-95% B (1.0 - 8.0 min), 95% B (8.0 - 8.5 min), 25% B (8.5 - 10.0 min) was employed. The MS/MS transitions and collision energy used for the analysis of the compounds were as follows: pinellinic acid m/z 329 \rightarrow 211 (22 eV), and internal standard PGE-f₂ α m/z 353 \rightarrow 193 (22 eV). The MS/MS transitions for linoleic acid used were ESI⁻ m/z 279 \rightarrow 58 and m/z 279 \rightarrow 261 (20 eV), and internal standard ¹³C₁₈-linoleic acid ESI⁻ m/z 297 \rightarrow 60 and m/z 297 \rightarrow 279 (22 eV).

Lipoxygenase activity

Twenty-five mg of flour was suspended in 1.5 mL of 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 6.6) in 2 mL Eppendorf tubes. The samples were vortexed and incubated in an ice-water bath for 1 h, followed by vortexing for 1 min at 15-minute intervals. The samples were then centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 20 min. The supernatant was collected as the crude enzyme solution and stored over an ice-water bath and used within 12 hours. The amount of crude enzyme was determined through the Bradford method utilizing bovine serum albumin (BSA) as a standard for the calibration curve.

Total lipoxygenase activity in whole grain wheat flour was measured using a modified colorimetric assay using the coupled reaction of 3-(di-methylamino) benzoic acid (DMAB) and 3-Methyl-2-benzothiazolinone (MBTH) as described by Anthon and Barrett [14]. The analysis was performed on 2 μ g of the crude enzyme as determined from the Bradford method. Stock solutions of 10 Mm MBTH in water, 5 mg/kg haemoglobin in water, 20 mM DMAB, 100 mM phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.0) were prepared and stored at 4 C. A solution of linoleic acid

stock was also prepared to contain 140 mg linoleic acid, 280 mg Tween 20, 0.6 mL of 1 N NaOH, and all diluted to a final volume of 20 mL with water.

The assay was performed at room temperature and two working solutions were prepared from the solutions listed above, working solution A (10 mL of 20 mM DMAB, 100 mM phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.0), 0.4 mL of 25 mM linoleic acid stock, and 9.6 mL water) and working solution B (0.4 mL of 10 mM MBTH, 0.4 mL 5 mg/mL haemoglobin, and 19.2 mL water). Sample (2 µg crude enzyme, about 5 µL sample) was incubated in 100 µL of solution A for 15 min. Then 100 µL solution B was added and samples were incubated for 10 min. The reaction was terminated by the addition of 100 µL of a 1 % (w/v) SDS. Negative controls were prepared by inactivation of the crude enzyme by heat treatment at 100 °C for 20 min. Blanks were prepared by an initial spike of 1% (w/v) SDS. Lipoxygenase activity was defined as the absorbance value at 598 nm per µg of protein times 1000.

Results and discussion

Lipoxygenase (LOX) plays an important role in biosynthetic pathways catalysing stereo-specific peroxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids containing *cis,cis*-1,4-pentadiene systems to their corresponding hydroperoxy derivatives, e.g., linoleic acid, to a hydroperoxide intermediate [15, 16]. To investigate the dependence of pinellic acid formation on lipoxygenase enzyme, wheat knockout lines (KO) were analysed. In addition to a LOX KO sample, a Lipase (LIP) KO sample was also analysed (linoleic acid formation); as well as a double LOX/LIP KO line. Figure 1 shows the LOX activity of the three KO samples compared to their wild sibling control samples. As expected, the LOX activity was significantly lower in the LOX and LIP/LOX KO samples, reporting a 96.4 and 94.1% lower activity, respectively, than the corresponding wild sibling controls.

The generation of pinellic acid in the dough samples made from the KOs and their wild sibling control wheat samples is reported in Figure 2. During bread making, pinellic acid is generated upon flour hydration [7,8]. The LOX and LIP/LOX KO significantly reduced the generation of pinellic acid, resulting in an 87.5 and 91.1% reduction in the compound concentration, respectively, then the corresponding wild sibling controls. The LIP KO had no significant impact on pinellic acid formation, indicating lipase activity did not impact the formation of this compound.

Figure 1: Comparison of flour lipoxygenase activity in lipase KO, lipoxygenase KO, and double KO of lipase and lipoxygenase vs their corresponding wild-type control; different letters indicate significant differences between wild sibling and KO ($p < 0.05$) according to Tukey's HSD; error bars represent standard errors.

Figure 2: Comparison of dough pinellic acid concentration in lipase KO, lipoxygenase KO and double lipase and lipoxygenase KO vs their corresponding wild-type control; different letters indicate significant ($p < 0.05$) according to Tukey's HSD; error bars represent standard errors.

While the analysis of the KO wheat samples indicated LOX as a key enzyme for pinellic acid formation, further analysis of a large wheat panel consisting of commercial samples was investigated to understand if lipoxygenase activity and linoleic acid (precursor) were predictive of product formation in the dough. Two hundred and twenty wheat different commercial variety samples developed over the past 140 years in the USA and grown in the same calendar year at the Wheat Genetic Resource Center at Kansas State University were analysed. The samples consisted of two wheat classes, hard red winter wheat (HRW) vs hard white winter wheat (HWW).

Analysis of the wheat panel reported the linoleic acid concentration in the flour ranged approximately 4-fold (363 to 1419 mg/kg) whereas the pinellic acid concentration in the dough ranged about 3-fold (97.9 to 304.4 mg/kg), however, no correlation was reported $R^2 = 0.018$ (Figure 3). These findings suggested the amount of the precursor, linoleic acid, was sufficient in whole wheat flour (in excess) and did not have a significant influence on the formation of pinellic acid in whole wheat dough samples.

Figure 3: Scatter plot of flour linoleic acid content versus dough pinellic acid concentration across 220 US hard wheat varieties.

Further analysis of the lipoxygenase activity across the wheat panel (ranged 4.2-fold) revealed no significant correlation with pinellic acid concentration ($R^2 = 0.0004$) (Figure 4). These results indicated the complex nature of the biosynthesis of this compound and the need for more understanding about the mechanisms, enzymes, and intermediate products involved, as multiple factors are likely implicated in the regulating flux of this pathway. Hamberg and Hamberg [17] outlined multiple oxidative enzymes involved in the biosynthetic route of linoleic acid to pinellic acid (LOX, peroxygenase, and epoxide hydrolase), thus provide other possible enzymatic 'bottlenecks' for product formation. Furthermore, wheat compounds could also modulate the activities of these key oxidative enzymes. Recently Cong et al. [18] reported an endogenous wheat compound schaftoside (apigenin di-C-glycoside) reduced the generation of pinellic acid during bread manufacture and decreased the perceived bitterness of whole wheat bread. They suggested schaftoside functioned as an allosteric inhibitor of lipoxygenase or epoxide hydrolase and suppressed the formation of hydroxylated fatty acids, such as pinellic acid.

Figure 4: Scatter plot of flour lipoxygenase activity versus dough pinellic acid concentration across 220 US hard wheat varieties.

Quantitative differences in the flour linoleic acid content and lipoxygenase activity, as well as the pinellic acid concentration in the dough, between the two wheat classes of hard red winter (HRW) and hard white winter (HWW) varieties were also evaluated and shown in Figures 5-7. No significant differences in concentration of linoleic acid were shown between red and white varieties (Figure 5) whereas the LOX activity was significantly higher in the HRW samples (Figure 6). However, no significant difference was reported in the pinellic acid

concentration reported in the dough (Figure 7), as expected from the lack of correlations reported between linoleic acid (Figure 3) and LOX activity (Figure 4).

Figure 5: Box plot of flour linoleic acid concentration in hard red winter wheat (HRW) vs hard white winter wheat (HWW) across 220 US wheat varieties.

Figure 6: Box plot of flour lipoxygenase activity in hard red winter wheat (HRW) vs hard white winter wheat (HWW) flour across 220 US wheat varieties.

Figure 7: Box plot of dough pinellic acid concentration in hard red winter wheat (HRW) vs hard white winter wheat (HWW) across 220 US wheat varieties.

Conclusion

Lipoxygenase was reported as a key enzymatic step in the formation of pinellic acid during bread making. However, variation in linoleic acid content (precursor) or lipoxygenase activity in commercial US wheat flour samples were not predictive of the pinellic acid content, indicating the other enzymatic steps (i.e. peroxygenase and epoxide hydrolase) or enzymatic modulation (i.e. allosteric inhibitors) impacted the generation of the bitter compound pinellic acid in wheat food products.

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